

IN-SITU MEASUREMENT OF RESIN STATE AND CURE FOR EFFICIENT NON-AUTOCLAVE MANUFACTURING

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ABSTRACT

Most thermoset resin matrices require rigorous control of environmental exposure prior to processing in order to limit out-time and moisture absorption. However, both requirements can be difficult to meet in industrial practice. In this paper, we investigate the effect of out-time and humidity exposure on the properties of a thermoset resin and investigate the monitoring of resin state before and during cure using real-time, in-situ dielectric measurements. We track dielectric properties as a function of out-time (0 to 5 weeks) and relative humidity (RH) from 30, 60, and 90%, and perform concurrent thermal analysis using traditional methods. The results indicate that moisture primarily influences the initial degree of cure with out-time, and leads to changes in flow time, gelation time, and reaction-end time. Moreover, the analysis shows that dielectric monitoring can capture changes in initial degree of cure, gel-time, and reaction-end time for the entire range of relative humidity studied in this paper, but that direct calculation of humidity levels from dielectric signals is difficult. Overall, the study clarifies the coupled effect of out-time and exposure to humid environments for a representative thermoset resin, and confirms the usefulness of in-situ dielectric property monitoring.

1 INTRODUCTION

Over the past decade, increasing use of composites has created a demand for manufacturing methods with lower costs, higher production rates and improved efficiency. Traditional approaches, including autoclave cure, are typically cost-prohibitive, rate-limiting and resource-inefficient [1]. As a result, alternative methods, including out-of-autoclave (OoA) prepreg processing and several liquid molding variants, have been proposed, demonstrated, and implemented in industrial settings [2]. Non-autoclave approaches often improve efficiency by eliminating infrastructure associated with the application of high external pressure (e.g. pressurized vessels for OoA prepregs or closed molds for vacuum resin infusion). Hence, such processes benefit from fewer “safeguards” against defect formation than traditional cure.

The manufacture of high quality, defect-free parts by non-autoclave processes therefore requires the development of defect mitigation strategies and technologies, including in-situ process monitoring [3, 4]. The accurate determination of the resin state prior to and during cure is particularly important, as resin properties govern in-process phenomena and have a substantial impact on final part quality and performance for all non-autoclave processes.

During pre-cure operations, the resin state can be affected by environmental factors such as temperature and ambient moisture. Exposure to room temperature conditions for extended periods, or “out-time”, can advance the degree of cure and viscosity of the resin and potentially prevent full infiltration of the fiber bed during cure [5, 6]. Out-time is particularly relevant to OoA prepregs, which were designed for large, integrated structures that often require several weeks to lay up prior to cure. Exposure to ambient humidity can lead to the rapid absorption of moisture. The dissolved water can then evolve during cure, causing the nucleation and growth of voids with internal pressures that exceed that which is imparted to the resin by non-autoclave processing. Moreover, moisture absorption

has also been shown to affect process-relevant properties such as degree of cure and viscosity by accelerating the polymerization/cross-linking reaction as both catalyst and solvent for the amine-epoxy reaction [7, 8]. It has been shown that water absorption can disrupt hydrogen bonds among segments of the polymers and cause swelling of the polymer, thus increasing the diffusion coefficient of water within the polymer which then reduces the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the polymers [7]. In addition, water can act as a catalyst facilitating epoxy-hydroxyl reaction [8].

During cure, the resin degree of cure evolves as polymerization/cross-linking takes place, leading to changes in all thermomechanical properties and controlling the progressive consolidation of the part. The accurate monitoring of this evolution, as well as the detailed understanding of the effects of pre-cure environmental exposure on resin properties, are desirable.

In this work, we use dielectric analysis (DEA) to monitor out-time at different environmental conditions for the case of an OoA prepreg material, and study the effects of conditioning on resin physicochemical changes during cure. The dielectric data is also analyzed and compared to measurements using traditional thermochemical and thermomechanical instruments to establish the validity of the analysis. The present study is relevant to a broader effort to exert greater control over prepreg manufacturing.

1.1 Out-Time (Out-life) & Humidity

Most resins used in OoA processing are pre-catalyzed, and therefore inherently unstable. At ambient temperature, such resins have been shown to undergo polymerization and cross-linking or cure [5, 9, 10]. Such advancement prior to cure can lead to incomplete prepreg impregnation during cure, high porosity, and lower mechanical properties at the cured stage. In previous studies [9, 10], we developed an out-time monitoring method by tracking heat of reaction, which decreases linearly as a function of out-time. Furthermore, our results showed that the processing-critical resin transitions (minimum viscosity, gelation and vitrification) gradually but significantly change during the out-life specified for the material.

Several authors have studied the effect of moisture absorption on cured parts [11 - 13]. In addition, the effect of humidity conditioning on parts processed by OoA techniques [14] has also been considered. However, despite their potential coupling, the effect of relative humidity (RH), the ratio of the partial pressure of water vapor to the equilibrium vapor pressure of water at the same temperature, and out-time on OoA prepreg resin thermochemical and thermomechanical properties during cure has not been studied.

1.2 Dielectric Analysis (DEA)

DEA can be used to accurately track the polymerization process of composite matrix resins [3, 4, 9, 10]. These studies examined real-time transformations in the dipole activity of the resin during cure at the molecular scale. Such measurements have been shown to identify both microscopic and macroscopic changes in key resin physicochemical parameters [3, 4, 9, 10]. In previous work [9, 10], we developed an effective method for detecting out-time and critical physicochemical events during cure. In this work, we investigate the use of our method for cases in which out-time is combined with significant moisture absorption prior to cure.

1.3 Objectives

The specific objectives of this study are to:

- (1) Develop and demonstrate a methodology for tracking prepreg subjected to out-time as well as various humidity levels using in-situ, real-time dielectric monitoring.

- (2) Correlate data obtained from traditional modulated dynamic scanning calorimetry (MDSC) and rheometry with *in situ* DEA to identify key thermochemical and thermophysical changes in resin cure kinetics, and viscosity as a function of both out-time and moisture absorption.

2 METHODS

2.1 Humidity Chamber

As an aqueous salt solution generates an equilibrium relative humidity (RH) in the head space of a closed container, a series of saturated salt solutions were prepared to achieve desired RH levels of 30, 60 and 90%. Appropriate salts targeting the desired RH were chosen according to the table by [15]. To prepare the saturated salt solution, salt was added to distilled water at 40 °C with stirring until no more salt dissolved. Then the solution is cooled to ambient temperature in a closed chamber and allowed to set until equilibrium RH was reached. RH values were measured using humidity meter.

2.2 Prepreg and Resin Conditioning

An OOA prepreg composed of eight-harness satin (8HS) carbon fiber fabric and a toughened epoxy resin (CYCOM[®] 5320-1, Cytec Industries, USA) was used for analysis. The manufacturer-specified out-life of the prepreg was 30 days. The initial out-time of all material was 0 days, and samples were stored frozen prior to use. Two types of samples were used to fit instrument constraints. Prepreg laminates measuring 30 × 30 mm were used for dielectric analysis, while neat resin was used for DSC, rheometry, and TGA. All samples were stored in humidity chambers with RH levels of 30, 60, to 90% for 0 to 5 weeks.

2.3 Modulated Dynamic Scanning Calorimetry (MDSC)

MDSC tests (TA Instruments Q2000) were conducted under a nitrogen purge. Sinusoidal temperature modulation on top of a linear temperature condition allows signal separation of the total heat flow into reversing and non-reversing components. The reversing component of heat flow depends on heat capacity and heating rate, while the non-reversing kinetic component directly indicates the cure exotherm [9]. For each dynamic measurement, a constant temperature ramp from -60 °C to 280 °C at a rate of 1.7 °C/min with a temperature modulation of ±0.5 °C/min was applied. For isothermal measurements, dwells were performed at 121 °C, and a temperature modulation of ±0.5 °C/min was applied over the dwell period.

2.4 Rheometry

Rheological measurements (TA Instruments AR2000) were performed using 25 mm aluminum parallel plates at a gap setting of 0.5 mm. All tests were conducted under constant oscillatory shear at a frequency of 1 Hz and at a strain of 0.25%, within the Newtonian plateau regime. Isothermal dwells were performed by heating at 10 °C/min to 121 °C and holding until 90% of the machine-specified maximum torque (200 mN·m) was required for shear displacement.

2.5 Dielectric Analysis (DEA)

A detailed description of DEA system used in this study has been published elsewhere [9, 10], while key characteristics are summarized below. A dielectric monitoring system based on coplanar interdigital electrodes (DETA SCOPE[™], ADVISE E.E., Greece) was used. Coplanar electrodes allow non-invasive and highly sensitive measurements by generating fringing electric field lines, whose penetration depth is controlled by the distance between opposing side electrodes. The electrode spacing in this study was designed to generate a fringing electric field depth (D) of 100 μm. This depth is proportional to the depth at which the sensor will penetrate through the dielectric material or the thermoset resin in carbon fiber fabric prepregs. However, as carbon fiber is electrically conductive, it

can interfere with the measurement if it comes into contact with the sensor. Thus, a 10 μm thick fiberglass surfacing veil was placed on the sensor side of the laminate to maintain a safe distance between the carbon fabric and the sensor while allowing resin to permeate through.

Prepreg samples were placed in a test cell consisting of the dielectric sensor, resistive heaters, and a monitoring and control system. Measurements were carried out by applying a sinusoidal voltage of 10 V while scanning twenty-five selected frequencies ranging from 1 Hz to 1 MHz. The measured signals were automatically converted to a useful immittance function—complex permittivity (ϵ^*)—which were subsequently converted to ionic conductivity (σ). Isothermal dwell measurements were made by applying heating ramp at 10 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ from 30 $^\circ\text{C}$ to 121 $^\circ\text{C}$ (the manufacturer's recommended dwell temperature), and maintaining the latter temperature uniformly until the end of cure. Dynamic ramp measurements were conducted by heating at 1.7 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ from 30 $^\circ\text{C}$ to 250 $^\circ\text{C}$. Although it is not specifically addressed in this paper, these dielectric sensors also can be embedded within traditional tooling and used, in the manner presented here, during oven processing, as well as for the monitoring of resin properties during various liquid molding processes.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Out-time Monitoring

Previous studies have shown that the major source of volatile in OoA prepreg resins is absorbed water and that voids grow via diffusion of water from surrounding resin [5]. To verify this, TGA results were compared to resin moisture contents measured by Fischer titration. Within the margin of error ($< 5\%$), the weight percent contents of water values measured by titration were equal to the values for total sample weight loss during TGA. As shown in Figure 1, the amount of water absorbed increased with RH. At equilibrium, roughly 0.9 wt% of water was absorbed for an RH of 90% while only 0.3 wt% for an RH of 30%. Therefore, at a molecular level, it is expected that samples conditioned at higher humidities will exhibit more changes associated with the catalytic/solvent effect.

Figure 1: Weight percent of water absorbed versus out-time at different humidity conditions (RH = 30, 60, and 90%)

The effect of absorbed moisture on the total heat of reaction (ΔH_{rxn}) and the B-stage glass transition temperature ($T_{g,0}$) during out-time are measured from MDSC and are displayed in Figure 2A and B. Water can act as both catalyst and solvent for resin polymerization/cross-linking. The results show that ΔH_{rxn} , which quantifies the exothermic heat release during resin cure, decreases with out-time at a predictable manner regardless of RH level. Resin conditioned at higher RH exhibited a sharper decrease in ΔH_{rxn} as absorbed water facilitated polymerization/cross-linking at ambient temperature. Such consistency allows prediction of initial degree of cure (α_0), defined in function of $\Delta H_{rxn,0}$ (the total heat of reaction at day 0) and $\Delta H_{rxn,t}$ (the total heat released at various out-times) [9]:

$$\alpha_0 = (\Delta H_{rxn,0} - \Delta H_{rxn,t}) / \Delta H_{rxn,0} \quad (1)$$

The initial glass transition temperature $T_{g,0}$ displays RH-dependent changes with out-time. Resin aged at RH of 90% exhibited a decrease in $T_{g,0}$ at day 7 and had lower $T_{g,0}$ than the resin aged at RH of 30% and 60% until day 21 despite its progression towards higher degree of cure (α). We presume this difference is caused by the solvent effect dominating over catalytic effect provided by water. Thus, tracking evolution of $T_{g,0}$ may not be a reliable way to track α_0 for resin exposed to variable environmental conditions.

Figure 2: (A) Total heat of reaction (ΔH_{rxn}) and (B) B-stage glass transition temperature ($T_{g,0}$) and on out-time

Dielectric analysis (DEA) data, in terms of logarithmic ionic conductivity ($\log(\sigma_m)$) as a function of out-time at 30 °C, is displayed in Fig. 3A. Subscript m is used to denote the mixture of water and resin. We assumed that the measured conductivity can be expressed as:

$$\sigma_m = w_r \cdot \sigma_r + w_w \cdot \sigma_w \quad (2)$$

where w_r and w_w are weight fraction of resin and water respectively and σ_r and σ_w are ionic conductivities of resin and water respectively ($\sigma_w = 2 \times 10^{-5}$ S/m at 30 °C). With this assumption and the known weight fraction of water in each sample (from TGA), σ_m and σ_w were plotted against α_0 (Figure 3B). Even though σ_w is four to five orders of magnitude greater than σ_r at 30 °C, its effect on the measured σ is limited by the low levels of absorbed moisture in the resin. Therefore, the measurement of ($\log(\sigma_m)$) remains an effective method of monitoring α_0 (Figure 3C) despite the substantial effect of water on α_0 during out-time. This result indicates that due to the low moisture absorption characteristic of this OoA prepreg, the accurate monitoring of out-time is possible even in challenging environments. For the case presented here, the relation between ($\log(\sigma_m)$) and α_0 is:

$$\log(\sigma_m) = A \cdot \alpha_0 + B \quad (3)$$

where A is -11.31 S/m and B is -8.79 S/m.

Figure 3: (A) Mixed conductivity (σ_m) versus out-time; (B) σ_m and resin conductivity (σ_r) versus initial degree of cure (α_0); and (C) σ_m versus α_0

3.2 Influence of Out-Time and Humidity on Cure Kinetics

To model cure kinetics, the total heat of reaction ($\Delta H_{rxn,0}$) was first determined from dynamic ramp (1.7 °C/min) data obtained from the sample with zero out-time. Assuming that the cure rate is directly proportional to the heat flow measurement, the cure rate is defined as [9]:

$$d\alpha/dt = (1/\Delta H_{rxn,0}) \cdot (dH/dt) \quad (4)$$

where α is the degree of cure, $d\alpha/dt$ is the cure rate and dH/dt is the total heat flow measured from MDSC. Integration of $d\alpha/dt$ versus time then yields α as a function of time ($\alpha(t)$), which ranges from 0 to 1, or fully-uncured to fully-cured.

Out-time is known to cause both time-based (horizontal) and magnitude (vertical) shifts of the cure kinetics profile, along with α_0 increases [10]. These effects are manifest in Figure 4, where Figure 4A and 4B show the cure kinetics profile changes of isothermal dwell measurement from 0 to 14 to 28 days of out-time at RH of 30 and 90% respectively. The cure kinetics of samples aged at 90% RH were more highly affected than those of samples exposed to 30% RH in terms of both time-based (horizontal) and magnitude (vertical) shifts.

The cure of thermoset resins can be conceived as a combination of fast kinetics-driven and slow diffusion-driven reactions. Thus, out-time, where the reaction is induced at low temperature, mainly affects kinetically driven reactions and its effect is more pronounced at higher RH levels, where absorbed moisture facilitates the reaction. The α versus cure time plots in Figures 4C and 4D show that due to α_0 increase, resins with higher out-time and RH conditioning reach reaction completion faster, but that all samples reached the same degree of cure (~69 %). The cure kinetics profile changes of samples cured using dynamic ramps after 0, 14 and 28 days of out-time at 30% RH and 90% RH are shown in Figure 5A and 5B. Similar shifts in reaction time and magnitude occurred, but their extent was greater than those observed in isothermal experiments. We posit that dynamic ramps provided sufficient instantaneous heat to overcome energy barriers associated with slow cure, and that absorbed moisture was vaporized sufficiently fast to limit its solvent effect. The α versus cure temperature results are plotted in Figures 5C and 5D.

Figure 4: Cure kinetics measurement of isothermal dwell at day 0, 14 and 28. Upper row – cure rate versus cure time: (A) RH = 30%, and (B) RH = 90%. Bottom row – degree of cure versus cure time: (C) RH = 30%, and (D) RH = 90%.

Figure 5: Cure kinetics measurement of dynamic ramp at day 0, 14 and 28. Upper row – cure rate versus cure time: (A) RH = 30%, (B) RH = 90%, and (C) comparison of RH = 30, 60, and 90% at day 28. Bottom row – degree of cure versus cure time: (D) RH = 30%, (E) RH = 90%, and (F) comparison of RH = 30, 60, and 90% at day 28.

3.3 Influence of Out-Time and Humidity on Viscosity

Viscosity (η) measurements are shown in Figure 6. Viscosity evolution is governed by two competing mechanisms: direct thermal effects and cross-linking. Initially, during heat-up, the rate of cure is minimal and the viscosity decreases due to increased molecular mobility. As the rate of cure increases, the effect of cross-linking and increased molecular size begins to dominate, and the viscosity increases. Such effects are evident from both isothermal dwells (Figures 6A and 6B) and dynamic ramps (Figures 6C and 6D).

Figure 6: Viscosity measurement of isothermal dwell and dynamic ramp at day 0, 14 and 28. Upper row – isothermal dwell: (A) RH = 30%, and (B) RH = 90%. Bottom row – dynamic ramp: (C) RH = 30%, and (D) RH = 90%.

Overall, viscosity levels increased with out-time, and the increases were greater in samples aged at higher humidity levels. These results imply that α_0 is the dominant factor that affects metrics of flow capacity such as flow time (t_{flow}), and gel-time (t_{gel}). In this work, we define t_{flow} as the time during isothermal dwells when resin viscosity is less than 100 Pa·s [2]. In Figure 7, t_{flow} is plotted against out-time at RH of 30, 60, and 90%. The t_{flow} decreased linearly against out-time at all humidity conditions and decreased more rapidly with higher humidity condition, supporting the hypothesis that t_{flow} is mainly affected by α_0 . Notably at 28 days of out-time, close to the out-life of the resin, t_{flow} ranges from 21.5 minutes at RH of 30% to 6.4 minutes at RH of 90%. As sufficient t_{flow} is required to fully infiltrate fiber beds and create void-free parts, these results indicate that humidity control or appropriate temperature control may be required for processing of aged parts. Gel-time or t_{gel} refers to the moment when an “infinitely large” crosslinked network of resin molecules is formed during cure. For epoxies, gelation is sometimes defined as the moment when viscosity reaches 10 kPa·s after passing minimum viscosity [9]. In this range, η increases quickly as cure effects dominate over thermal effects, and rheometric measurements are constrained by the limits of machine torque. This result is discussed in the following section.

Figure 7: Flow-time (t_{flow}) versus out-time at RH = 30, 60, and 90% during isothermal dwell.

3.4 Influence of Out-Time and Humidity on Ionic Conductivity

Thermoset resins contain significant amounts of ionic impurities introduced during resin preparation [3, 4, 9, 10]. Thus, the resin transformation from a liquid-like to a solid-like state due to out-time will cause a measurable decrease in σ . In contrast to rheological measurements, DEA involves measurement of ionic species motion, thus avoiding the limitations associated with material viscosity/stiffness near gelation.

Ionic conductivity data for isothermal dwells at out-times of 0, 14 and 28 days are plotted in Figure 8A and 8B for RH = 30% and 90% respectively. Generally, out-time led to a decrease in σ . In addition, the decrease was greater for resin aged in more humid environments. Consistent with our previous hypothesis, the conductivity of water did not dominate the overall conductivity of the mixture. Increased α_0 due to the catalytic/solvent effect caused by absorbed moisture affected overall conductivity the most during isothermal dwells. Figure 8C compares the evolution of σ at RH of 30, 60, and 90% at day 28, and further confirms this mechanism.

Figure 8: Ionic conductivity (σ) change during isothermal dwell at day 0, 14 and 28: (A) RH = 30%, (B) RH = 90%, and (C) comparison of RH = 30, 60, and 90% at day 28.

Figure 9A shows the correlation between out-time, gel-time (t_{gel}) from DEA signals, and reaction end time (t_{rxn}) from DEA and MDSC for isothermal dwelling. t_{gel} is defined as the inflection point in the plot of $\log(\sigma)$ versus cure time. This point corresponds to the maximum rate of σ change, which corresponds to the maximum decrease in ionic mobility during cure [9]. t_{rxn} is taken as the point where no further change in σ is observed. Similarly, t_{rxn} using MDSC is defined as $d/dt(da/dt) = 0$. In Figures 8B and 8C (9B and 9C), closed and open symbols correspond to traditional and DEA measurements, respectively. The t_{gel} comparison shows close correlation between the two methods with a high degree

of accuracy for a quadratic relation of the form: $t_{gel} = f(t, RH, T)$ where t is out-time, RH is relative humidity, and T is isothermal dwell temperature. Conversely, a discrepancy of roughly 20 min was observed for all t_{rxn} with all RH and out-time studied between MDSC and DEA (Figure 9C). We posit that it is caused by the low sensitivity of DEA monitoring near the end of reaction, as the resin solidifies and stiffens, and the uniformity of the deviation supports this hypothesis. Consequently, for the purpose of monitoring reaction end-times, a constant off-set should be added to t_{rxn} measured with DEA.

Figure 9: Isothermal dwell measurement of: (A) Demonstration of gel-time (t_{gel}) and reaction end time (t_{rxn}) analysis using DEA (B) t_{gel} versus out-time (closed symbol: rheometry and open symbol: DEA), and (C) t_{rxn} versus out-time (closed symbol: MDSC and open symbol: DEA).

4 CONCLUSIONS

We have described the effects of moisture and out-time on the evolving properties of a thermoset resin for non-autoclave (OoA prepreg) processing, and investigated the feasibility of *in-situ* dielectric monitoring of the resin state for conditioned material. First, conventional *ex-situ* methods (MDSC and rheometry) were used to collect benchmark data. Subsequently, *in-situ* dielectric analysis was conducted to gain a more detailed understanding of the physical phenomena involved, and to verify which phenomena can be detected in real-time. The results indicate that moisture mainly affects the initial degree of cure during out-time, and consequently decreases flow time, gelation time, and reaction-end time. Therefore, humidity control or appropriate thermal control to ensure flow time required to fully saturate the composite matrix during processing may be required to create quality parts. In addition, we observed that DEA allows accurate monitoring of initial degree of cure, gel-time, and reaction-end time for the entire range of relative humidity studied in this paper, confirming the robustness of the previously proposed methodology. However, our results also indicated that, for this combination of material and instrument, the direct calculation of absorbed humidity levels from dielectric signals prior to cure is difficult due to the relatively small change in ionic conductivity with moisture intake. Note that for dielectric monitoring to be more effective in terms of process monitoring, predictive models that comprehensively capture out-time and humidity effects on cure kinetics and viscosity in process conditions are required. These issues are discussed elsewhere [16].

Altogether, this work shows that DEA is an effective and robust method of assessing material out-time prior to cure and monitoring the evolution of key resin properties at elevated temperatures. DEA and other *in-situ* processing methodologies offer opportunities to accurately control process inputs, detect unwanted and potentially damaging deviations from ideal conditions, and reduce defect levels, scrap rates and resource use. As a result, they contribute to improved process effectiveness and efficiency in composite manufacturing.

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